

Questionnaire on drift visualization methods

In the following you are asked to decide which visualization methods reveal drifts in sensor data streams to help a user decide if the sensor data stream is behaving as desired. If changes in the underlying distribution of data in a streaming environment occur over time, it is called concept drift [1].

[1] J. Lu, A. Liu, F. Dong, F. Gu, J. Gama, and G. Zhang, "Learning under concept drift: A review," IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering, pp. 1–1, 2018. doi: 10.1109/tkde.2018.2876857. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1109%2Ftkde.2018.2876857.

* Indicates required question

1. How many years of experience do you have in the field of business process management? *

2. What is your primary area of expertise within business process management? *

General Explanation of The Drift Visualization Methods

The following image shows a sample visualization of a drift at a specific timestamp. The first recorded time series is shown as blue line ("trace 1") and the last recorded time series as an orange line ("trace 40"). The red dot marks the point that is currently selected to show detailed drift visualization.

The arrows (inside the yellow circle) show in which direction this particular point drifted. As 39 arrows (trace 1 to 40) would be hardly perceivable, the traces are grouped (average time series - ats) and averaged so that each arrow represents the average drift over 5 (default setting but can be changed) traces. The difference between the most current trace (orange line - "trace 40") and the average of the most recent 5 average traces is highlighted as a light green shaded area (in our case "ats 8").

[Enlarge image](#)

Machining V2: the 90 degree angles method

Scaling factor (min: 1) Offset (min: 0)

Data point at timestamp 1

The images below show the visualization of a drift at timestamp 1 with three slightly different visualization methods.

Each one consists of 3 images:

- Image 1 (leftmost image) shows the visualization of a drift at a certain timestamp as explained in the last section.
- Image 2 (image in the middle) which shows details for the particular drift, which is displayed when hovering over the arrow
- Image 3 (rightmost image) shows that the length of the arrows can be scaled to show the amount of drift better. While the arrows in image 1 overlap a lot, as the drift might go back and forth, image 3 demonstrates how to offset the arrows to prevent that overlap. This is done by offsetting the arrows vertically (light, strictly vertical lines connecting the arrows in image 3).

Please answer the following statements for three slightly different visualization methods that follow the principles described above.

3. 90 Degree Visualization Method *

[Enlarge image](#)

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Can you easily identify in which direction measurements have drifted?	<input type="radio"/>					
Can you easily identify the overall amount of drift that occurred?	<input type="radio"/>					
Can you easily identify individual drift amounts between certain grouped traces (e.g., between traces 6-10 and 11-15)?	<input type="radio"/>					
Are the details displayed for a certain drift (arrow) useful?	<input type="radio"/>					
Is the offset helpful in identifying individual drift amounts?	<input type="radio"/>					

4. Shortest Distance Visualization Method *

[Enlarge image](#)

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Can you easily identify in which direction measurements have drifted?	<input type="radio"/>					
Can you easily identify the overall amount of drift that occurred?	<input type="radio"/>					
Can you easily identify individual drift amounts between certain grouped traces (e.g., between traces 6-10 and 11-15)?	<input type="radio"/>					
Are the details displayed for a certain drift (arrow) useful?	<input type="radio"/>					
Is the offset helpful in identifying individual drift amounts?	<input type="radio"/>					

5. Same Timestamp Visualization Method *

[Enlarge image](#)

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Can you easily identify in which direction measurements have drifted?	<input type="radio"/>					
Can you easily identify the overall amount of drift that occurred?	<input type="radio"/>					
Can you easily identify individual drift amounts between certain grouped traces (e.g., between traces 6-10 and 11-15)?	<input type="radio"/>					
Are the details displayed for a certain drift (arrow) useful?	<input type="radio"/>					
Is the offset helpful in identifying individual drift amounts?	<input type="radio"/>					

6. Please sum up the strengths and weaknesses of each of the three approaches (shown above) when visualizing the drift at timestamp 1.

Data point at timestamp 1.55

The images below show the visualization of a drift at timestamp 1.55 with three slightly different visualization methods.

Each one consists of 3 images:

- Image 1 (leftmost image) shows the visualization of a drift at a certain timestamp as explained in the last section.
- Image 2 (image in the middle) which shows details for the particular drift, which is displayed when hovering over the arrow
- Image 3 (rightmost image) shows that the length of the arrows can be scaled to show the amount of drift better. While the arrows in image 1 overlap a lot, as the drift might go back and forth, image 3 demonstrates how to offset the arrows to prevent that overlap. This is done by offsetting the arrows vertically (light, strictly vertical lines connecting the arrows in image 3).

Please answer the following statements for three slightly different visualization methods that follow the principles described above.

Please note that the 3 images below are for the same traces, BUT a different point in the trace is selected (red dot). Each visualization method might be better or worse for that particular point.

7. 90 Degrees Visualization Method *

[Enlarge image](#)

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Can you easily identify in which direction measurements have drifted?	<input type="radio"/>					
Can you easily identify the overall amount of drift that occurred?	<input type="radio"/>					
Can you easily identify individual drift amounts between certain grouped traces (e.g., between traces 6-10 and 11-15)?	<input type="radio"/>					
Are the details displayed for a certain drift (arrow) useful?	<input type="radio"/>					
Is the offset helpful in identifying individual drift amounts?	<input type="radio"/>					

8. Shortest Distance Visualization Method *

[Enlarge image](#)

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Can you easily identify in which direction measurements have drifted?	<input type="radio"/>					
Can you easily identify the overall amount of drift that occurred?	<input type="radio"/>					
Can you easily identify individual drift amounts between certain grouped traces (e.g., between traces 6-10 and 11-15)?	<input type="radio"/>					
Are the details displayed for a certain drift (arrow) useful?	<input type="radio"/>					
Is the offset helpful in identifying individual drift amounts?	<input type="radio"/>					

9. Same Timestamp Visualization Method *

[Enlarge image](#)

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Can you easily identify in which direction measurements have drifted?	<input type="radio"/>					
Can you easily identify the overall amount of drift that occurred?	<input type="radio"/>					
Can you easily identify individual drift amounts between certain grouped traces (e.g., between traces 6-10 and 11-15)?	<input type="radio"/>					
Are the details displayed for a certain drift (arrow) useful?	<input type="radio"/>					
Is the offset helpful in identifying individual drift amounts?	<input type="radio"/>					

10. Please sum up the strengths and weaknesses of each of the three approaches (shown above) when visualizing the drift at timestamp 1.55.

Data point at timestamp 4.75

The images below show the visualization of a drift at timestamp 4.75 with three slightly different visualization methods.

Each one consists of 3 images:

- Image 1 (leftmost image) shows the visualization of a drift at a certain timestamp as explained in the last section.
- Image 2 (image in the middle) which shows details for the particular drift, which is displayed when hovering over the arrow
- Image 3 (rightmost image) shows that the length of the arrows can be scaled to show the amount of drift better. While the arrows in image 1 overlap a lot, as the drift might go back and forth, image 3 demonstrates how to offset the arrows to prevent that overlap. This is done by offsetting the arrows vertically (light, strictly vertical lines connecting the arrows in image 3).

Please answer the following statements for three slightly different visualization methods that follow the principles described above.

11. 90 Degrees Visualization Method *

[Enlarge image](#)

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Can you easily identify in which direction measurements have drifted?	<input type="radio"/>					
Can you easily identify the overall amount of drift that occurred?	<input type="radio"/>					
Can you easily identify individual drift amounts between certain grouped traces (e.g., between traces 6-10 and 11-15)?	<input type="radio"/>					
Are the details displayed for a certain drift (arrow) useful?	<input type="radio"/>					
Is the offset helpful in identifying individual drift amounts?	<input type="radio"/>					

12. Shortest Distance Visualization Method *

[Enlarge image](#)

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Can you easily identify in which direction measurements have drifted?	<input type="radio"/>					
Can you easily identify the overall amount of drift that occurred?	<input type="radio"/>					
Can you easily identify individual drift amounts between certain grouped traces (e.g., between traces 6-10 and 11-15)?	<input type="radio"/>					
Are the details displayed for a certain drift (arrow) useful?	<input type="radio"/>					
Is the offset helpful in identifying individual drift amounts?	<input type="radio"/>					

13. Same Timestamp Visualization Method *

[Enlarge image](#)

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Can you easily identify in which direction measurements have drifted?	<input type="radio"/>					
Can you easily identify the overall amount of drift that occurred?	<input type="radio"/>					
Can you easily identify individual drift amounts between certain grouped traces (e.g., between traces 6-10 and 11-15)?	<input type="radio"/>					
Are the details displayed for a certain drift (arrow) useful?	<input type="radio"/>					
Is the offset helpful in identifying individual drift amounts?	<input type="radio"/>					

14. Please sum up the strengths and weaknesses of each of the three approaches (shown above) when visualizing the drift at timestamp 4.75.

Comparison with the raw data visualization

The images show all traces at the timestamps which have been used for the previous questions. The first image shows the traces around timestamp 1, the second image displays the traces around timestamp 1.55 and the third image shows the traces around timestamp 4.75.

[Enlarge image](#)

The images show all traces which have been used for the previous questions at the timestamp 1 and the 3 drift visualization methods used for the previous questions. The first image shows all traces around timestamp 1 and the other three images show from left to right the 90 degree method, the shortest distance method and the same timestamp method for visualizing the drift at timestamp 1.

[Enlarge image](#)

15. A concept drift is easier to spot with the raw data visualization than with the... *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
...90 degrees visualization method.	<input type="radio"/>					
...shortest distance visualization method.	<input type="radio"/>					
...same timestamp visualization method.	<input type="radio"/>					

Detection of important points

Until now images which emphasize the drift for a single points were shown. In the following the focus will be on which points should be chosen to apply the presented visualization methods.

For the following questions the traces are split into one group of OK cases (blue/gray) and one group of not OK cases (red). Blue is the average time series of the sensor measurements of OK cases while red is the average time series of sensor measurements of not OK cases.

On the y-axis the (absolute) difference between the average time series of traces which are OK and traces which are not OK is shown for different timestamps. The orange vertical lines split the time sequence into segments based on where OK and not OK have a difference which is close to zero.

16. Which segments should be considered in order to determine whether a trace is more similar to the average time series of OK traces or not OK traces? *

Check all that apply.

- Segment A
- Segment B
- Segment C
- Segment D
- Segment E
- Segment F
- Segment G
- Segment H
- It does not make sense to decide this based on the provided data

17. Explain based on which criteria you chose which segments to pick or not to pick.

Check all that apply.

- Length of the segment (how did that influence your decision)
- Single data points inside the segment (which one)
- Behavior of the time series inside the segment (which behavior)
- Other: _____

18. If you want to you can elaborate on your answer.

On the y-axis the (absolute) difference between the average time series of traces which are OK and traces which are not OK is shown for different timestamps. The orange vertical lines split the time sequence into segments based on where the difference between OK and not OK traces is close to zero. The vertical green lines show potentially interesting points in the time series.

19. Which of the timestamp(s) would you examine in more detail if your goal is to find out if a trace belongs to the OK or not OK traces?

Check all that apply.

- Point A
- Point B
- Point C
- Point D
- Point E
- Point F
- Point G
- Point H
- Point I
- Point J
- Point K
- Point L
- Point M
- Point N
- Point O
- Point P
- Point Q
- It does not make sense to decide this based on the provided data
- Other: _____

20. Explain based on which criteria you chose which points to pick or not to pick.

Check all that apply.

- Timestamp of the point
- Value of the point independent of its neighbors
- Value of the point in comparison to its neighbors
- Point is in a specific segment
- Other: _____

21. If you want you can elaborate on your answer.

On the y-axis the value of measurements of one sensor can be seen over time (x-axis). The vertical green lines show potentially interesting points in the time series.

22. Which of the timestamp(s) would you examine in more detail if your goal is to find out if a trace belongs to the OK or not OK traces?

Check all that apply.

- Point A
- Point B
- Point C
- Point D
- Point E
- Point F
- Point G
- Point H
- Point I
- Point J
- Point K
- It does not make sense to decide this based on the provided data
- Other: _____

23. Explain based on which criteria you chose which points to pick or not to pick.

Check all that apply.

- Timestamp of the point
- Value of the point independent of its neighbors
- Value of the point in comparison to its neighbors
- Other: _____

24. If you want you can elaborate on your answer.

Analysis of a Single Trace

The image shows the sensor values of a measurement in a single trace (blue line) along with the average sensor values of the same measurement among all traces which are OK (orange line) and all traces which are not OK (green line).

25. Based on this image do you think the trace (blue line) belongs to the OK or not OK cases? *

Mark only one oval.

- OK
- not OK
- undecidable

26. Please describe how you arrived at your decision.

Analysis of a Single Trace Using the 90 Degree Method

The blue points in the image represent the (absolute) difference between the OK and not OK time series when the 90 degree method is used for calculating this distance. The orange lines separate the whole time series into segments by using the timestamps where the difference is zero or close to zero as criterion.

All potentially interesting points (indicated by a vertical green line in the picture below) are shown in the diagram below.

In the following, the distance between the single trace and OK and not OK time series is displayed in the form of arrows. **Green arrows** show the distance to OK parts, **red arrows** show the distance to not OK parts.

The following pictures show the distance of a point in the trace to the average OK or average not OK time series while viewing the whole time series on the left side and a zoom in on the point on the right side.

Please indicate which particular points you would use if you had to decide if the single analyzed trace belongs to the group of OK or not OK traces.

27. Use point A? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

28. Use point B? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

29. Use point C? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

30. Use point D? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

31. Use point E? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

32. Use point F? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

33. Use point G?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

34. Use point H? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

35. Use point I? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

36. Use point J? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

37. Use point K? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

38. Use point L? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

39. Use point M? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

40. Use point N? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

41. Use point O? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

42. Use point P? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

43. Use point Q? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

44. Based on the chosen points do you think the trace belongs to the OK or not OK cases? *

Mark only one oval.

- OK
- not OK
- undecidable

45. Should other points also be considered? If yes, which points (use estimated timestamp)?

46. Please describe based on which criterion you chose which points to use and how you came up with your decision if the trace belongs to the OK or not OK traces based on these points.

Analysis of a Single Trace Using Shortest Distance Method

The blue points in the image represent the (absolute) difference between the OK and not OK time series when the shortest distance method is used for calculating this distance. The orange lines separate the whole time series into segments by using the timestamps where the difference is zero or close to zero as criterion.

All potentially interesting points (indicated by a vertical green line in the picture below) are shown in the diagram below.

In the following, the distance between the single trace and OK and not OK time series is displayed in the form of arrows. **Green arrows** show the distance to OK parts, **red arrows** show the distance to not OK parts.

The following pictures show the distance of a point in the trace to the average OK or average not OK time series while viewing the whole time series on the left side and a zoom in on the point on the right side.

Please indicate which particular points you would use if you had to decide if the single analyzed trace belongs to the group of OK or not OK traces.

47. Use point A? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

48. Use point B? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

49. Use point C? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

50. Use point D? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

51. Use point E? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

52. Use point F? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

53. Use point G?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

54. Use point H? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

55. Use point I? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

56. Use point J? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

57. Use point K? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

58. Use point L? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

59. Use point M? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

60. Use point N? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

61. Use point O? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

62. Use point P? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

63. Use point Q? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

64. Use point R? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

65. Based on the chosen points do you think the trace belongs to the OK or not OK cases? *

Mark only one oval.

OK

not OK

undecidable

66. Should other points also be considered? If yes, which points (use estimated timestamp)?

67. Please describe based on which criterion you chose which points to use and how you came up with your decision if the trace belongs to the OK or not OK traces based on these points.

Analysis of a Single Trace Using Same-Timestamp Method

The blue points in the image represent the (absolute) difference between the OK and not OK time series when the 90 degree method is used for calculating this distance. The orange lines separate the whole time series into segments by using the timestamps where the difference is zero or close to zero as criterion.

All potentially interesting points (indicated by a vertical green line in the picture below) are shown in the diagram below.

In the following, the distance between the single trace and OK and not OK time series is displayed in the form of arrows. Green arrows show the distance to OK parts, red arrows show the distance to not OK parts.

The following pictures show the distance of a point in the trace to the average OK or average not OK time series while viewing the whole time series on the left side and a zoom in on the point on the right side.

Please indicate which particular points you would use if you had to decide if the single analyzed trace belongs to the group of OK or not OK traces.

68. Use point A? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

69. Use point B? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

70. Use point C? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

71. Use point D? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

72. Use point E? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

73. Use point F? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

74. Use point G?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

75. Use point H? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

76. Use point I? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

77. Use point J? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

78. Use point K? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

79. Use point L? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

80. Use point M? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

81. Use point N? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

82. Use point O? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

83. Use point P? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

84. Use point Q? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

85. Based on the chosen points do you think the trace belongs to the OK or not OK cases? *

Mark only one oval.

- OK
- not OK
- undecidable

86. Should other points also be considered? If yes, which points (use estimated timestamp)?

87. Please describe based on which criterion you chose which points to use and how you came up with your decision if the trace belongs to the OK or not OK traces based on these points.

Analysis of Another Single Trace

The image shows the sensor values of a measurement in a single trace (blue line) along with the average sensor values of the same measurement among all traces which are OK (orange line) and all traces which are not OK (green line).

Analysis of Another Single Trace Using the 90 Degree Method

The blue points in the image represent the (absolute) difference between the OK and not OK time series when the 90 degree method is used for calculating this distance. The orange lines separate the whole time series into segments by using the timestamps where the difference is zero or close to zero as criterion.

All potentially interesting points (indicated by a vertical green line in the picture below) are shown in the diagram below.

88. Use point A? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

89. Use point B? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

90. Use point C? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

91. Use point D? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

92. Use point E? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

93. Use point F? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

94. Use point G? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

95. Use point H? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

96. Use point I? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

97. Use point J? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

98. Use point K? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

99. Use point L? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

100. Use point M? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

101. Use point N? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

102. Use point O? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

103. Use point P? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

104. Use point Q? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

105. Based on the chosen points do you think the trace belongs to the OK or not OK cases? *

Mark only one oval.

- OK
- not OK
- undecidable

106. Should other points also be considered? If yes, which points (use estimated timestamp)?

107. Please describe based on which criterion you chose which points to use and how you came up with your decision if the trace belongs to the OK or not OK traces based on these points.

Analysis of Another Single Trace Using the Shortest Distance Method

The blue points in the image represent the (absolute) difference between the OK and not OK time series when the 90 degree method is used for calculating this distance. The orange lines separate the whole time series into segments by using the timestamps where the difference is zero or close to zero as criterion.

All potentially interesting points (indicated by a vertical green line in the picture below) are shown in the diagram below.

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Please indicate which particular points you would use if you had to decide if the single analyzed trace belongs to the group of OK or not OK traces.

108. Use point A? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

109. Use point B? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

110. Use point C? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

111. Use point D? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

112. Use point E? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

113. Use point F? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

114. Use point G?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

115. Use point H? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

116. Use point I? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

117. Use point J? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

118. Use point K? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

119. Use point L? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

120. Use point M? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

121. Use point N? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

122. Use point O? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

123. Use point P? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

124. Use point Q? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

125. Use point R? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

126. Based on the chosen points do you think the trace belongs to the OK or not OK cases? *

Mark only one oval.

- OK
- not OK
- undecidable

127. Should other points also be considered? If yes, which points (use estimated timestamp)?

128. Please describe based on which criterion you chose which points to use and how you came up with your decision if the trace belongs to the OK or not OK traces based on these points.

Analysis of Another Single Trace Using the Using Same-Timestamp Method

The blue points in the image represent the (absolute) difference between the OK and not OK time series when the 90 degree method is used for calculating this distance. The orange lines separate the whole time series into segments by using the timestamps where the difference is zero or close to zero as criterion.

All potentially interesting points (indicated by a vertical green line in the picture below) are shown in the diagram below.

In the following, the distance between the single trace and OK and not OK time series is displayed in the form of arrows. Green arrows show the distance to OK parts, red arrows show the distance to not OK parts.

The following pictures show the distance of a point in the trace to the average OK or average not OK time series while viewing the whole time series on the left side and a zoom in on the point on the right side.

Please indicate which particular points you would use if you had to decide if the single analyzed trace belongs to the group of OK or not OK traces.

129. Use point A? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

130. Use point B? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

131. Use point C? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

132. Use point D? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

133. Use point E? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

134. Use point F? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

135. Use point G?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

136. Use point H? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

137. Use point I? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

138. Use point J? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

139. Use point K? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

140. Use point L? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

141. Use point M? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

142. Use point N? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

143. Use point O? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

144. Use point P? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

145. Use point Q? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

146. Based on the chosen points do you think the trace belongs to the OK or not OK cases? *

Mark only one oval.

- OK
- not OK
- undecidable

147. Should other points also be considered? If yes, which points (use estimated timestamp)?

148. Please describe based on which criterion you chose which points to use and how you came up with your decision if the trace belongs to the OK or not OK traces based on these points.

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